

Original Article

Proprietary and Patent Medicine Vendors in Lassa Fever Endemic Communities in Edo State, Nigeria: Assessment of Knowledge, Exposure Risk and Potential for Inclusion in Outbreak Response

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ABSTRACT

Background: The study investigated the knowledge and attitude of proprietary and patent medicine vendors (PPMVs) towards Lassa fever (LF) and related practices to ascertain their risk of infection and potential role in community-based control.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted in Esan West and Esan Central local government areas of Edo State, Nigeria. Data were collected using self-administered questionnaires, and Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used for analysis.

Result: 182 out of 200 administered questionnaires were retrieved and analysed. All respondents had heard of LF. About 35.2% (64/182) of respondents had inadequate knowledge with predictors as tertiary education (AOR = 0.11, P = 0.024), and age > 35 years (AOR = 0.07, P = 0.001). About 74.2% (135/182) expressed their willingness to educate clients on Lassa fever. About 66.5% had used a sharp device in the past 6 months, with 33.9% being an injection device. In the preceding 3 months, one-fifth encountered at least a client who did not recover after a first course of treatment for malaria. Of this, two-fifth were referred to a health facility for further care. Injection practices, hand glove use and hand hygiene were sub-optimal for 26.8% (11/41), 42.1% (51/121) and 67.6% (123/182) of respondents, respectively. Waste segregation was improper for 80.8% (147/182) of respondents.

Conclusions: PPMVs, though knowledgeable about LF, held unsafe work practices. Interventions to address gaps in knowledge and infection control practices will protect them against contracting LF and position them to actively participate in LF control.

Key words: Chemist, Drug vendor, Patent Medicine Vendor, Lassa fever, Proprietary, Practices

INTRODUCTION

The private health sector in many developing countries is the main source of health care for acute conditions and includes proprietary and patent medicine vendors (PPMVs)^{1,2}. They are persons without formal training in pharmacy licensed to sell over-the-counter medicines and medical products as a retail business venture^{3,4}. At different times, there have been calls for the inclusion of PPMVs into community-based preventive services for communicable diseases, to complement the activities of the formal health sector including the Malaria Control Programme⁵, Tuberculosis Control Programme⁶ and more recently, the COVID-19 pandemic response^{7,8}.

PPMVs are a potential, yet unoptimized resource for community-based Lassa fever (LF) control activities, especially for case recognition, client education, counselling and referrals⁴. Including the PPMVs in LF control activities, however, requires an assessment of what they know and their willingness to be involved.

Many PPMVs extend their services to include sales of prescription-only drugs, medical consultations, injections and minor surgical procedures⁹⁻¹¹. These practices increase their risk of contracting LF especially when infection control practices are flouted, underscoring the need to empower them to adopt safe work practices. So far, there is limited information on PPMVs and LF. This study sought to assess the health literacy and attitudes of PPMV towards LF, and identify work-related practices that expose them to infection with the virus.

Methods

Study area and design

This cross-sectional study was carried out in Esan West and Esan Central Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Edo State, Nigeria. Edo State accounts for the highest number of LF cases in Nigeria^{12,13}. These LGAs are hotspots for Lassa fever and contribute up to 30% of the cases reported in the State¹⁴. Esan West LGA occupies a land mass of 502 km² and has a 2016 estimated population of 167,300 residents across 10 political wards. Esan Central LGA has a population of 137,900 and a land mass of 253 km². Residents are mainly subsistence farmers and small-scale traders in general goods.

Patent medicine stores operate mainly as sole proprietor businesses registered under the Pharmacist Council of Nigeria (PCN) and the National Association of Patent and Proprietary Medicine Dealers (NAPPMED). Their operational time usually spans 12-15 hours each day, with between 1-3 workers. At the time of the study, there were 272 registered patent medicine stores in both LGAs.

Study population and sample size

The study was conducted between January 2019 and September 2019 with the study population as persons working in patent medicine stores. Selection criteria included age >18 years, being present at the time of the study, willingness to give consent and work history of ≥6 months as a PPMV.

The minimum sample size was approximated as 200 using the formula for finite populations¹⁵, z^2pq/d^2 , with p as 50% in the absence of previous studies on PPMVs and LF, 5% margin of error and 95% confidence interval and applying the correction formula for populations less than 10,000, $nf = no/[1 + no/N15]$, with a 10% adjustment for non-response.

Sampling and Data collection

Retail shops were selected through a simple random sampling process from the list of registered drug stores obtained from both LGAs. In each selected store, one eligible person was recruited, and where more than one eligible person was present, simple random sampling was used to select one. If the contacted person declined, a new selection was made for a replacement.

Data were collected using a structured English language interviewer-administered questionnaire designed by the researchers after a critical review of literature on the subject matter^{3,16-18} and with input from experts in the field of infectious diseases and epidemiology. The questionnaire was divided into four sections: I – socio-demographic information including gender, age, marital status, religion, educational level, years of experience as a PPMV and formal health-related or pharmacy training. Section II had 13 questions on knowledge of Lassa fever including the agent, vector, incubation period, mode of transmission in the community and healthcare setting, symptoms, name of drug used to treat confirmed cases, methods of prevention in the community and the existence of a vaccine.

Respondents were required to choose one of three responses: 'Yes', 'No' or 'I don't know'. Responses for knowledge of Lassa fever were scored one (1) if correct and zero (0) if incorrect (either 'no' or 'I don't know') with a total possible score of 31. Knowledge was dichotomized as 'adequate' if a respondent's score was $\geq 50\%$ of the total and 'inadequate' for individual summed scores $< 50\%$ of the total for knowledge. Section III had 5 questions on attitude towards LF with responses on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 'strongly agree' to 'strongly disagree'. Questions for attitude were positively worded and coded as '1' for 'strongly disagree', '2' for 'disagree', '3' for 'uncertain', '4' for 'agree' and '5' for 'strongly agree'.

For analysis, attitude scores were rated on a 25-point scale and graded as negative if the respondent's total score was ≤ 12 and positive if ≥ 13 . The Cronbach alpha for the 5 items on the attitude scale was 0.74. Section IV sought information on the respondent's encounter with a client who experienced treatment failure for a febrile illness in the preceding 3 months before the survey.

Section V assessed the use of sharps in the last 6 months and related infection control practices. The latter was assessed through 4 domains including (a) hand hygiene practices (5 questions including upon arrival at work, after using the toilet, before a clean activity, after coughing or sneezing, after a dirty activity such as wound dressing) (b) injection safety practices (6 questions to assess needle manipulation, recapping, use of a sharp box, boiling and giving an injection to an agitated patient) (c) use of hand glove when handling soiled items or body fluids (1 question) (d) Waste segregation (1 question).

Response options for all 4 domains were provided as 'always', 'infrequently' and 'never'. Questions for injection safety were negatively worded so responses were dichotomized such that 'always' and 'infrequently' responses were scored '0', while 'never' was assigned a score of '1'. On the other hand, for hand hygiene, waste segregation and glove use, questions were positively worded so that 'always' was scored '1' while 'infrequently' and 'never' were scored '0'. The maximum score for injection safety practices, hand hygiene and glove use were 6, 5 and 1 respectively. For injection safety practices, a respondent's score within 0-3 was graded as suboptimal and ≥ 4 as optimal.

A score between 0-2 for hand hygiene was graded as suboptimal while ≥ 3 were graded optimal. For glove use, 0 was graded as suboptimal and 1 as optimal. An affirmative response to the question on waste segregation was scored '1' and labelled proper, while a negative response was scored '0' and labelled as improper.

Risk levels for contracting LF and other infectious diseases for each of the 4 domains of infection control practice were assessed using a qualitative 3 x 3 risk matrix¹⁹. The risk level was calculated as the product of the likelihood that harm will occur from the infection control breach (hazard) and the severity of such harm. The likelihood was assessed using the responses 'always', 'infrequently' and 'never' from the practice questions as a proxy for probability. Likelihood was graded low when a protective activity was carried out always, medium when carried out infrequently, and high when a protective activity was never carried out. Severity was qualitatively assessed and graded as low (first aid, exposure to minor health risk, little or no economic costs incurred), medium (reversible injury but requiring medical treatment, involves loss of time and money) and high (death or irreversible health impact, substantial economic and time loss). Risks with a ranking of 1 were classified as low, 2 as medium, 3 as high and 5 as critical¹⁹. Figure 1.

Likelihood	High	Medium 2	High 3	Critical 5
	Medium	Low 1	Medium 2	2
	Low	Low 1	Low 1	Medium 2
		Low	Medium	High
		Severity		

Fig. 1: Risk matrix¹⁹

Face and content validity of the questionnaire was assessed by two experts from the Public Health Department of Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital, while the questionnaire was pretested for readability and comprehension among 10 PPMVs in Esan Northeast LGA. Distribution to consenting participants was done by final-year medical students engaged as research assistants who had been trained on the study protocol and tools.

Data analysis

The data were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY, USA). Normally distributed continuous variables were presented as mean (standard deviation SD), while non-normally distributed continuous variables were presented as median (with 25th and 75th quartiles). Categorical variables were presented as Bar charts, frequencies and percentages. Associations between knowledge of LF and sociodemographic variables were tested using Pearson's Chi-square test. Variables with a p-value < 0.2 were modelled in multivariable logistic regression.

Ethical considerations

Approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital. Participation was voluntary and without compensation. Participants were provided written information on the study and written informed consent was obtained.

Participants were duly informed that participation was voluntary and without compensation and that they were free to opt-out of the study at any time. Study tools were anonymized for confidentiality purposes.

Results

One hundred and eighty-two questionnaires out of 200 distributed were returned giving a response rate of 91.0%. The median age was 32.0 (26.4) years, 79 (43.3%) respondents were aged between 25 – 44 years, 128 (70.3%) respondents were males, 59 (65.6%) were married and 96 (52.7%) had tertiary education, 53 (29.1%) respondents had a health-related professional background. The mean (Standard deviation, SD) number of years of experience as a PPMV was 8.9 (9.3) years. (Table 1). All respondents had heard of LF with the most mentioned source of information as the health worker, 93 (52.0%), and least mentioned as family members 7 (3.9%). The median knowledge score was 19 (IQR 14, 22). LF knowledge was adequate for 118 (64.8%) respondents and inadequate for 64 (35.2%) respondents. The proportion of respondents who gave correct answers to the questions on methods of spread, methods of prevention of LF in the community and the type of vector were more than those who gave incorrect answers. Conversely, more respondents gave incorrect answers to methods of spread and prevention in health facilities, incubation period, treatment and availability of a vaccine than those who gave correct answers. The frequencies of correct and incorrect responses to the LF knowledge questions are shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents (n = 182)

Variable	Frequency (%)
Age group (years)	
<24	28 (15.4)
25 -34	79 (43.4)
35-44	36 (19.8)
>45	39 (21.4)
Mean age (SD)	34.3 (12.5)
Sex	
Male	128 (70.3)
Female	54 (29.7)
Religion	
Christianity	78 (86.7)
Islam	12 (13.3)
Educational attainment	
Primary	8(4.4)
Secondary	78 (42.9)
Tertiary	96 (52.7)
Marital status	
Married	120 (65.9)
Single	62 (34.1)
Years of experience as a PPMV	
<5	99 (54.4)
6-14	44 (24.2)
15-24	22 (22.1)
≥25	17(9.3)
Training in orthodox healthcare	
No	129 (70.9)
Yes*	53 (29.1)

*Includes nurses and Community health extension workers (CHEW),

About 74.7% (136 /182) of respondents agreed LF was a public health problem, 30.2% (55/182) were not confident they could recognize a case of LF and 61.5 % (112/182) opined that PPMVs should not treat LF cases. Majority, 74.2% (135/182) expressed their willingness to educate clients on LF (Table 3).

Overall, attitude towards LF was positive for 110 (60.4%) and negative for 72 (39.6%) respondents. Multivariable regression analysis showed that respondents aged 35- 44 years and those >45 years were 0.07 and 0.27 times likely to have inadequate knowledge compared to those < 24 years ($p= 0.001$ and $p= 0.034$, respectively). Respondents with a tertiary level of education were 0.11 times likely to have inadequate knowledge compared to those with a primary level of education ($p= 0.024$). Respondents with work experience >25 years were 0.08 times likely to have a negative attitude towards LF compared to those <5 years ($p= 0.007$, 95% CI 0.01-0.50). Respondents with inadequate knowledge were 10.67 times likely to have negative attitudes compared to those with adequate knowledge ($p< 0.001$, 95% CI 5.05-22.05), Table 4.

Twenty-eight (15.4%) out of 182 respondents recalled that in the preceding 3 months, they had at least one client who had a febrile illness that did not respond to treatment. Of this number, 18 (64.3%) respondents referred the client to a hospital for further investigation, 6 (21.4%) repeated the course of treatment and 2 (7.1 %) directed the client to non-orthodox treatment.

Table 2: Lassa fever (LF) knowledge domains (n = 182)

Knowledge items	Correct response n (%)	Incorrect response n (%)
The vector of Lassa fever is a rat	173 (95.1)	9 (4.9)
The agent of Lassa fever is a virus	81 (45.5)	101 (54.5)
The incubation period of Lassa fever	22 (12.1)	160 (87.9)
Modes of transmission of Lassa fever in the community		
Rat bite	87 (47.8)	95 (52.2)
By eating rodents	125 (68.7)	57 (31.3)
by spreading food uncovered in the open	142 (78.0)	40 (22.0)
by eating/drinking contaminated food	155(85.2)	27 (14.8)
Eating with unwashed hands	139 (76.4)	43 (23.6)
Using unwashed utensils/plates contaminated with the virus for eating	145 (79.7)	37 (20.3)
How is Lassa fever spread in healthcare settings?		
Contact with dead bodies	106 (58.2)	76 (41.8)
Contact with body fluids of someone sick with Lassa fever	105 (57.7)	77 (42.3)
Unsafe sharps management	98 (53.8)	84(46.2)
Poor waste disposal	114 (62.6)	68 (37.4)
Symptoms of Lassa fever include:		
High grade fever	133 (73.1)	49 (26.9)
Bleeding	93 (51.1)	89 (48.9)
Headache	101 (55.5)	81 (44.5)
Vomiting	124 (68.1)	58 (31.9)
Facial swelling	70 (38.5)	112 (61.5)
Muscle pain	87 (47.8)	95 (52.2)
Mention 3 methods of prevention in the community		
Avoid bush burning	144 (79.1)	38 (20.9)
Store food covered	156 (85.7)	26 (14.3)
Good personal hygiene	171 (94.0)	11 (6.0)
Mention at least 3 methods of prevention in the healthcare facility	138 (75.8)	44 (24.2)
Use of dedicated equipment for infected patients	122 (67.0)	60 (33.0)
Proper waste disposal	115 (63.2)	67 (36.8)
Isolation of patients	116 (63.7)	66 (36.3)
Use of personal protective equipment	134 (73.6)	48 (26.4)
What drug is used to treat Lassa fever?	29 (15.9)	153 (84.1)
A Lassa fever vaccine is currently available.	57 (31.3)	125 (68.7)

Table 3: Responses to attitudinal statements towards Lassa fever (n = 182)

Attitudinal statements	Strongly agree n (%)	Agree n (%)	Uncertain n (%)	Disagree n (%)	Strongly disagree n (%)
Lassa fever is a public health problem in this country	96 (52.7)	40 (22.0)	23 (12.6)	12 (6.6)	11 (6.0)
I am at risk of contracting Lassa fever from my clients	48 (26.4)	39 (21.4)	35 (19.2)	45 (24.7)	15 (8.2)
It is not a waste of time and money to create awareness of Lassa fever among patent medicine vendors	81 (44.5)	56 (30.8)	9 (4.9)	20 (11.0)	16 (8.8)
I am confident I can identify a case of Lassa fever	20 (11.0)	35 (19.2)	53(29.1)	51 (28.0)	23 (12.6)
I do not think I should treat Lassa fever in my store	51 (28.0)	61 (33.5)	33 (18.1)	7 (16.5)	30 (3.8)

Table 4: Logistic regression of predictors of knowledge and attitude towards Lassa fever

Variable	Knowledge			Attitude		
	AOR	P-value	95% CI	AOR	P-value	95% CI
Age group (years)						
≤24	1			1		
25 -34	0.36	0.062	0.12-1.05	0.66	0.444	0.22-1.94
35-44	0.07	0.001*	0.01-0.32	0.55	0.390	0.14-2.15
≥45	0.27	0.034*	0.08-0.90	1.81	0.398	0.46-7.17
Educational attainment						
Primary	1			-	-	-
Secondary	0.17	0.063	0.03-1.10	-	-	-
Tertiary	0.11	0.024*	0.02-0.75	-	-	-
Religion						
Christianity	1			1		
Islam	0.00	0.998	-	0.96	0.950	0.26-3.52
Years of experience as a PPMV						
≤5				1		
6-14	-	-	-	1.38	0.475	0.57-3.30
15-24	-	-	-	2.06	0.225	0.64-6.63
≥25	-	-	-	0.08	0.007*	0.01-0.50
Training in orthodox healthcare						
No	1			-	-	-
Yes	1.18	0.704	0.51-2.70	-	-	-
Knowledge of Lassa fever						
Adequate	-	-	-	1		
Inadequate	-	-	-	10.67	<0.001*	5.05-22.50

*significant at multivariable analysis

One hundred and twenty-one (66.5 %) respondents had used at least one type of sharp in the past 6 months including surgical blade, razor, needle and syringe, cannula and lancet. Of this number, 41 (33.9%) had given injectable medication including anti-tetanus serum, 111 (91.7%) administered first aid with wound dressing, and 25 (20.7%) drained an abscess. Among the respondents who had given an injection, unsafe injection practices recorded included needle manipulation 4 (9.8%), needle recapping 31 (75.6%), improper disposal of syringe and needle, 26(63.4%) and giving an agitated patient an injection, 9 (22.0%). No respondent had shared needles between clients nor boiled needles for reuse. Overall, 26.8% (11/41) of respondents who had given injectable medication had injection safety practices graded as suboptimal. Four (9.8%) out of 41 respondents reported a needle stick injury in the past 6 months, of which 2 (50.0%) received post-exposure prophylaxis.

The practice of wearing hand gloves when in contact with potentially infectious material was sub-optimal for 42.1% (51/121) of respondents who gave a history of handling sharps. Hand hygiene practice was suboptimal for 67.6% (123/182) and waste segregation graded as improper for 147 (80.8%) respondents, Figure 2. The risk level for the majority was graded as medium for the injection safety domain (71.2%), low for the waste segregation domain (64.3%), medium for the hand hygiene domain (35.2%) and medium for the use of hand glove domain (57.9%).

Fig. 2: Infection control practices of respondents

DISCUSSION

The study assessed the knowledge and infection control practices of PPMVs who are often first responders to persons seeking health care in the community. Approximately 3 out of 5 PPMVs were knowledgeable and willing to participate in LF control. Approximately 3 out of 5 rendered services that involved the use of sharps, with poor injection safety practices, suboptimal use of hand gloves, hand hygiene and poor waste segregation.

Expectedly all respondents had heard of LF, as has been reported in some studies carried out among health workers^{20,21} and in contrast to other studies where some health workers had not heard of Lassa fever^{22,23}. The study location being endemic for LF with yearly response activities that include public enlightenment, it is understandable that the level of awareness was high. However, as people migrate to and from the study area, sensitization should be an all-year-round activity and not limited to outbreak periods. Similar levels of knowledge of the disease as observed in this study were reported in studies carried out among healthcare workers across tertiary, secondary and primary healthcare levels in Edo, Ondo and Ebonyi States^{20,24} and contrast with other studies where lower levels of knowledge were observed^{22,25–27}. These differences may be ascribed to the publication age, type of facility and cadre of health workers.

Fever was the most common symptom reported as was similarly observed in other studies^{28,29}. Since fever is a symptom of most tropical diseases, PPMVs need to be conversant with other symptoms of LF to be able to refer clients who meet the suspect case definition. Most respondents did not know the drug used for the treatment of LF, in tandem with finding from some earlier studies^{22,30} and in contrast with others^{27,28}. While PPMVs are not expected to treat LF, it is beneficial for them to know the name of the drug used to treat LF as they often counsel and provide clinical advice to their clients, and this information may be sought by a client. As PPMVs may be the first responders to cases of LF in a community and provide clinical services albeit illegally, they are more likely to contract the disease from clients. It becomes imperative that they know how to protect themselves from infection, not only from LF but from other pathogens.

Interventions to reduce the knowledge gaps identified by this study should include tailored trainings provided to all, with attention paid to those with primary and secondary educational levels and younger aged PPMVs as these factors were predictors of poor knowledge. The significantly lower levels of knowledge among the two groups may be because people with lower levels of education have less health literacy and comprehension, and younger PPMVs might not have been in the field long enough to be exposed to information on LF.

The predominantly positive attitude towards LF observed in this study has been documented in previous studies^{25,30} and is a good foundation for further engagement of PPMVs in the LF response. Interestingly, few respondents expressed confidence that they could recognize a case of Lassa fever, just as less than a quarter could recall an encounter with a suspected case in the last 3 months. Some studies^{4,23} have similarly noted the low proportion of health workers who had ever reported a suspected case of LF. This underscores the need for PPMVs to be provided with pictographs of suspected cases, useful for quick reference. They could be taught to recognize symptoms, enquire about an exposure history and provide appropriate health advice. Their willingness to talk to clients about LF is commendable and should be maximized. Previous studies have documented the potential benefits that can be gained by training PPMVs and including them in public health interventions^{8,31,32}. The feasibility or otherwise of their inclusion into LF community-based interventions requires further elaboration.

The large proportion of respondents who referred patients who failed to respond to treatment for febrile illness agrees with a previous study where 57% of PPMVs referred febrile children who did not improve after malaria treatment to a health facility¹¹. However, the referral of sick persons to non-orthodox centres should be discouraged through health education. An incentive could be provided to PPMVs who refer clients that eventually test positive for LF as a way of motivating them to continue the practice.

It is worrisome that slightly above half of the respondents were uncertain or disagreed that they were at risk of contracting LF. This denial may indeed make them less vigilant and inadvertently at risk. A similar finding was reported in a study among primary care providers where 42.7% of respondents felt knowledgeable enough to manage LF²².

This contrasts with a previous study where the majority of health workers perceived themselves to be at risk of contracting LF³⁴.

The clinical procedures practised by PPMVs in this study have been documented in earlier studies^{3,35–37} and are a reflection of the weak enforcement of regulations that guide the operations of patent medicine stores. With the possibility that some of their clients may have been LF cases as reported in this study, these illicit practices, coupled with the suboptimal compliance to basic IPC measures reported in the study, increase the risk of contracting LF and its spread within the community.

Poor IPC compliance was also documented among PPMVs in Southeast Nigeria³, in contrast to a study carried out during a LF outbreak in Kaduna where IPC practices were good for the majority of health workers interviewed²⁵.

Notably, risk levels for the 4 domains were either medium or high. These findings underscore the need for PPMVs to be trained in the basic practice of infection control, and stricter measures put in place to limit their scale of operations to what the regulations guiding their establishment permit. A study to determine factors responsible for poor infection control practices is necessary.

The study has some limitations. Esan West and Esan Central LGAs were purposively selected so the findings may not be generalizable to other LGAs where LF is not endemic. As information about IPC practices was collected retrospectively, recall bias cannot be ruled out. The IPC practices were also self-reported and were not observed, so may not be a true reflection of what happens.

In conclusion, PPMVs had adequate knowledge and a positive attitude towards LF. However, beyond the sale of drugs, they undertook minor procedures with poor IPC compliance that placed the majority of them at medium to high risk of infection. That notwithstanding, the majority expressed their willingness to be part of the LF response. Training on LF and IPC and enforcement of regulations guiding the operations of patent medicine stores are necessary to reduce their risk. The feasibility of including PPMVs in LF response activities at the community level, particularly in the areas of community sensitization, active case search and referrals of suspected cases should be explored.

DECLARATION

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Author Contributions : EAT and VA designed the research study. EAT, VA, and AO collected the research data. EAT and AO analyzed the data. EAT, VA, and AO wrote the paper. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript

Ethical approval : Approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital.

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